

IN-SERVICE TRAINING AND SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ILORIN METROPOLIS, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study investigated the relationship between in service training and school effectiveness in private secondary schools in Kwara state. The research designed for this study was a descriptive research of correlational type. The population for the study comprised all 605 teachers and all students in the thirty-eight duely registered private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. Proportional random sampling technique was used to select 300 respondents from fifteen private secondary schools. Questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. The instrument was trial-tested to obtain reliability coefficient of 0.68. A checklist was also designed to collect five year results of students in West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) from the sampled schools (2011-2015). Two research questions formulated were answered using tables and frequent count. Three hypotheses generated were tested using computer SPSS and inferential statistical method at 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that, there was a positive significant relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness in private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. There is a significant relationship between in-service training and student academic performance. Also, there was a positive relationship between in-service training and teacher job performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended that proprietors of private secondary schools should release their teachers promptly for in-service training programme. They should also give financial assistance to teachers willing to go for training programme in order to encourage them and further enhance their job performance.

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Keywords: in-service training, teacher job performance, students academic performance and school effectiveness

1. Introduction

School management is concerned with the mobilization of both human and material resources in order to accomplish the school objective. Human resources represent the most important variable in the school system due to the fact that it is the human resource of an institution that ultimately influence the character and speed of its effectiveness towards enhancing the desire Students' Academic Performance which is the yardstick through which the stakeholders measure the school effectiveness. The degree of qualified graduates produced will depend on the quality of its human resources, particularly the teachers. Afolabi (2004) citing Harbison (1973) said that human resources constitute the ultimate basis for the wealth of nations. Capital and natural resources are passive factors of production; human beings are the active agents who accumulate capital, exploit natural resources, built economic and political organization, and carry forward national development. Clearly a country which is unable to develop the skill and knowledge of its people and utilize them effectively in her national economy will be unable to develop anything else. This assertion was shared by Tijani (2013) who saw teachers as the productive instrument in the school system.

Oyededeji (2012) while describing management in education, maintained that men and materials devoted to education must be controlled for the purpose of attaining effective teaching and learning in educational institutions. From this assertion, it is clear that the most important school objective is better student academic performance which stems out from effective teaching and learning. To accomplish this therefore, teachers in this industry must be well trained and retrained so as to be able to face the new challenges of our educational system. Teachers are important variable for the survival of our educational system as they are to implement the curriculum. Without inspiring trained and re-trained teachers, there can be no hope of successfully meeting the challenges of a dynamic educational system in the world. George (2006) said training is to assist the teachers to acquire knowledge and skills needed to be effective on the job. Training employs some methods to give old and new teachers added skill and knowledge to perform their job effectively and efficiently.

Ofoegbu (2017) identified some rationale for training and development as to increase workers' productivity, develop high morale, increase future personal needs, enhance personal growth, enhance institutional growth, and reduce institutional and personal supervision. In short, in-service training is designed to improve the skills and qualities of teachers in the school system. It is on this premise therefore, that the study focuses on the relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness in private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis Kwara state. However, the school effectiveness will be measured in terms of students' academic performance and the teachers' job performance.

The use of school effectiveness is an abstract measure of performance. It evaluates the conditions under and the degree to which schools are attaining their various goals. This concept provides a useful indication of the ability of the schools to be effective in term of effectiveness of teachers in their job performance and the attainment of academic excellence as the end result. Effectiveness in institution of learning depends on the specific organizational characteristics. School effectiveness entails relevance of programmes, and cognitive development of the students.

2. Literature Review

In-service training is a fundamental continuing processes a modern management tool used to solve manpower problems in organization and influence changes in the level of job performance (Tijani, 2013). Some years back, new employees were expected to pick-up necessary job skills and knowledge from experienced fellow employees. This method of training certainly did not work well and it caused the learning process to be very slow. Some worker deliberately kept back information, important skill and knowledge in order to protect their position and status I the organization. Nowadays, companies run schools of their own, they arrange for special course, pay tuition for in-service training programs and correspondence courses, often they pay their staff for the time spent in attending classes.

Similarly, Alabi (2000) stressed that staff training and development activities are engaged in by school personnel to enhance their knowledge, skills and attitudes. The immediate aim of staff development is to improve the performance of those with teaching and management responsibilities, while the ultimate aim is improvement of teaching and learning. According to Alabi (2000), the first training a new employee receives is called orientation which is in the form of introduction that provides a new employee with general information about the organization's rules, practices, policies and procedures that will affect him on job. In-service training assists the worker to measure up to standard on his job, increase his value to the organization and satisfy his human need for personal growth on the job. Training of any kind has therefore become the instrument of instruction used by organization on employee on the specific job he is to perform.

Aderinola (1986) in Tijani (2013) believed that if employees are progressively trained, accident, spoilt work, absenteeism, complaint and dissatisfaction will be greatly reduced. The workers will experience satisfaction associated with a sense of achievement and knowledge as they are developing their interest and capability at work due to the adequate training they acquired. This implies that employees will increase their response to continued training and thereby prepare themselves adequately for promotion. In-service training could then be seen as a way of helping the employee to develop, adapt, learn new methods, use new kinds of equipment and adjust to major changes in the job contents.

According to Ogunsaju (2000), to minimize wastage, employees have to be hired and trained with the purpose of serving their organization. According to him, the

requirement for human resources are identified in terms of quality of personnel to be employed. This implies that adequately qualified teachers must be employed in school system and in-service training while proper monitoring system must be put in place to develop them so as to ensure school effectiveness. Thus, in-service training is a procedure for improving teachers' ability and capability in their job performance. It is designed to raise their performance with an improve knowledge, value, skills and competence as they are expose to new method of teaching. Ogunsaju (2000) further described effectiveness as the degree to which employees attain both short and long term goals. Relating this to the school system, effectiveness refers to task accomplishment and the degree at which a teacher carries out the assigned duties of teaching and learning. This study therefore measure teacher's job performance in terms of the teaching.

Alabi (2000) affirmed school as a formal organization where knowledge and skill are acquired. Its staff, especially teacher must be subjected to a progressive and continuous training and development. Therefore, schools have a role to play in the development of human knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that would make man productive. The quality of education provides in schools, depend directly on the capacity, commitment and motivation of teachers. The quality of learning depends on the recruitment, retention and development of professional teachers among other who are needed to improve the level of performance towards the provision of quality education. Nowadays, effectiveness of school is measured in terms of teachers' effectiveness, which indicates the level of their job performance as revealed by the students' academic performance. The teacher's job performance on the other hand, is seen in terms of the use of appropriate instructional materials, class control, teachers' mastery of the subject, discipline and the use of appropriate teaching methodology. In-service training could therefore be identified as the necessary tools, which would improve teacher-job-performance towards attaining the objectives of the school. Since in-service training programme is to improve knowledge and skills of workers, it is then seen as an instrument designed to support and assist the professional development that workers especially teachers ought to experience throughout their teaching carrier.

In essence, managing is an organizational leadership and one of its central task is effective co-ordination, training and development of available human resource so as to achieve the objectives of the organization. Progressive training is an important instrument that must be carried out by management of the school. This statement was summarized by Oyedeji (1998) who described the job of personnel manager as an understanding of people as individuals and as group, selecting the right men for the job and assessing, motivating and training the subordinates.

Many researchers have examined the reasons for the disparity in the level of measures. Many factors have been deduced by researchers to responsible for school effectiveness. Some of the factors identified are supervision of instruction, quality of school facilities, poor teaching method employed by teachers, poor attitude of students to learning among others. For instance, Abdulkareem (1989) in Afolabi (2004) investigated into the impact of school resources management and school effectiveness in

selected Kwara State Secondary Schools. AbdulKareem Seven indicators of school effectiveness were identified in terms of managerial performance in the areas of planning, organizing, staffing, controlling and communicating. Effectiveness is the capacity and ability of an organization to accomplish the correct end. Effectiveness encompasses the quality and quantity of output. Applying this definition to the educational system, the school is effective if it is tailored towards the quality of pupils. The pupils are likely to be of high quality. Effectiveness is therefore related to how a school is able to attain academic excellence through teachers job performance.

Aremu (2000) discovered factors like parental influence, poor method of teaching and poor instructional materials as determinants of students' academic performance. Ofeimu, Kolawole and Omoike (2016) identified in-service training as an influence of students academic performance in Edo Central senatorial district secondary schools. The present study however, investigates relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness in Ilorin metropolis private secondary schools. The teacher job performance and students' academic performance were the variables used to measure the school effectiveness. Thus becomes a gap that this study tends to fill.

3. Statement of the Problem

In recent years, several studies in Nigeria revealed poor students' academic performance in their final year West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) especially in Public Secondary Schools. The occurrence has been attributed to poor teachers' job performance in these schools. This forced many parents to enroll their children in Private Secondary Schools which acclaimed to be more effective with better student academic performance. Besides, in recent years, Kwara State government embarked on re-training of teachers, the effect of which some people believed has not been justified by the performance of the students. This accounts for the reason why the study is out to look into the relationship between in - service training and school effectiveness in private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis of kwara state.

3.1 Research Questions

- 1) What is the level of Teachers' Job performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools?
- 2) What is the level of Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools?

3.2 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

H₁: There is no significant relationship between In-service training and school effectiveness in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between In-service training and teachers' job performance in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between In-service training and Students' Academic Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state.

4. Methodology

The study was a descriptive research of correlational type. It establishes the relationship between in-service training and schools effectiveness in Kwara State private secondary schools. This method provides opportunity for the researchers to elicit information on the relationship that exists between the two variables-in-service training and School effectiveness.

The population for this study comprised of all private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis that have formally registered with the State Ministry of Education and that have been graduating students prior to the year 2015. The sample consists of 15 schools drawn from the 38 private secondary schools in the metropolis using stratified random sampling technique. 300 teachers were selected from 605 that cut across the 15 secondary schools using proportional random sampling technique.

Questionnaire was the basic instrument used to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part is concerned with the bio-data of the respondents while the second part deals with information on in-service training and school effectiveness in private secondary schools. Close-ended type of questionnaire was used in which options were supplied and the respondents were to tick the most appropriate one. The instrument was validated by three experts from Department of Educational Management and trial tested to ascertain its content validity. However, the reliability co-efficient of 0.68 was obtained through Pearson product-moment correlation statistics. The researchers produced 300 questionnaires which were distributed to the teachers of the sample schools in the ratio of the number of teachers in each school. The administration of this instrument was done by the researchers and also through the assistance of some teachers. The researchers used Statistical Package of Social Science(SPSS) to obtain p-values which were compared with 0.05 level of significance to determine the acceptability of the generated hypotheses and to analyze the results from all the hypotheses generated for this study.

5. Findings and Discussion of Result

Research Question 1: What is the level of Teachers' Job Performance?

Table 1: Level of Teachers' Job Performance in Ilorin metropolis private secondary school

Response	Frequency	Percentage
High	181	60.3
Moderate	79	26.3
Low	40	13.4
Total	300	100

Table 1 revealed the level of teachers' job performance as perceived by students of private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. 181 of the respondents representing (60.3%) were of the opinion that the level of teachers' performance towards their academic achievement was high. The teachers were rated high as regards the usage of the modern teaching methodology, mastery of the subject matter and engagement in the co-curricular activities in the schools. 79 (26.3%) and 40 (13.4%) of their teachers as moderate and low respectively. The interpretation of this result is that the job performance of teachers in Ilorin metropolis private secondary schools was high. The high level of teacher job performance could be attributed to different firms of In-service training attended.

Question 2: What is the level of Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools?

The following bench mark was used to determine the level of Students' Academic Performance:

- High: 5 credits and above (including English Language and Mathematics);
- Medium: 4 credits – 5 passes (including Mathematics and English);
- Low: 3 credits and below.

Table 2: Students Academic Performance in Private Secondary Schools

Response	Frequency	Percentage
High	2765	64.7
Moderate	1052	24.6
Low	458	10.7
Total	4275	100

Source: Fieldwork

Table 2 indicated the level of Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools. The final year results of West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) obtained from the selected schools showed that 4,275 students results released for the years understudy 2,765 representing (64.7%) had 5 credits and above including English Language and Mathematics. This thus shows high level of performance of students in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis. However, 1,052 (24.6%) between 4 credits and 5 passes including English Language and Mathematics. This thus indicated medium level of Students' Academic Performance. It was also observed that 458 students representing (10.7%) had 3 credits and below and hence low level of performance. It could be therefore be deduced that there was high level of Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools.

5.1 Hypothesis Testing

H₁: There is no significant relationship between In-service Training and School Effectiveness in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools.

Table 3: Correlation analysis of In-service Training and School Effectiveness in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis

Variables	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	DF	Calculated r-value	P-value	Decision
In-service training	300	29.42	1.99	298	288	0.0000	Rejected
School effectiveness	300	30.56	2.81				

P<0.05

Table 3 revealed that the calculated p-value of 0.0000 was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null-hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness is rejected. Therefore, In-service training has a positive significant relationship with school effectiveness in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools. This implies that In-service training is a determinant of school effectiveness. The interpretation of this result is that any forms of In-service training that gears towards improving teachers' skills competences, capacity and intelligent will induce their job performance and hence, enhance Students' Academic Performance as measures of school effectiveness. Additional teacher qualification on the subject area will improve the teaching methodology, class control, knowledge of subject matter and thereby enhance the teaching and learning and thus school effectiveness.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between In-service training and teachers' job performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools.

Table 4: Correlation analysis of In-service training and Teachers-job-performance

Variables	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	DF	Calculated r-value	P-value	Decision
In-service training	300	30.45	2.90	298	.199	0.0000	Rejected
School effectiveness	300	32.56	2.81				

P<0.05

Table 4 indicated that the calculated p-value of 0.01 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null-hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between In-service training and teacher job performance is thereby rejected. Hence, there was a positive significant relationship between In-service training and teacher job performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools.

Thus In-service training is a determinant of teacher job performance. The interpretation of this result is that as teacher acquires new skills, knowledge and competence, their job performance will be stimulated and thereby enhance their performance in both curricular and co-curricular activities in the school.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between In-service training and Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools.

Table 5: Correlation analysis of In-service Training and Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin metropolis Private Secondary Schools

Variables	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	DF	Calculated r-value	P-value	Decision
In-service training	300	31.42	1.99	298	218	0.01	Rejected
School effectiveness	300	32.56	2.80				

P<0.05

Table 5 showed that the calculated p-value of 0.01 was less than the significant level of 0.05, therefore, the null-hypothesis which states that there was no significant relationship between In-service training and Academic Performance in Ilorin Private Secondary Schools is hereby rejected. Hence, there was a positive significant relationship between the two variables. This result implies that In-service training is a determinant of Students' Academic Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Ilorin metropolis. The simple interpretation of this is that as In-service training improves teachers' knowledge, skills and teaching methodology on the subject matter so also enhance the students understanding and thus their performances in examinations.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

In the analysis of data, all the hypotheses tested gave lower calculated p-value as compared with 0.05 level of significance signified the rejection of the null-hypotheses.

From the result, the following summary can be drawn:

- 1) There is a positive significant relationship between in-service and school effectiveness in private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state.
- 2) There is a positive significant relationship between in-service training and student's academic in Ilorin metropolis private secondary schools, Kwara state.
- 3) There is a positive significant relationship between in-service training and teacher job performance in Ilorin metropolis private secondary schools, Kwara state.

6. Conclusion

Efficiency of any school depends to a large extent on the quality of its teacher as they are important input in any school system. In-service training is therefore becomes essential instrument that enhance the efficiency of teachers in-terms of new skills, knowledge and thus improve the school effectiveness.

Teachers are responsible for survival of our school system. Without quality and re-trained teachers, there can be no hope for a successful and effective school system in the country. This account for the reason why the National Policy on Education gives due recognition to the significance of teacher in its section 9 sub-section 57 which states that *"no education can rise above the quality of its teachers"*.

This findings of this study revealed that there is positive significant relationship between in-service training and school effectiveness (students academic performance) termed from the appropriate teaching methodology. For this reason, it could be

concluded that In-service training has a major role to play at enhancing quality of teachers and thus school effectiveness.

6.1 Recommendations

The various stake holders in the educational system are interested in schools with better annual academic performance especially at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE). Realizing the role of in-service training to improving the quality of teachers' towards school effectiveness, the researchers therefore, offered the following suggestions to proprietors of private secondary schools and government.

- 1) Proprietors of private secondary schools should release their teachers promptly for in-service training and the teachers should take the programme with all seriousness.
- 2) The school proprietors should sponsor or give financial assistance to teachers willing to go for training programme.
- 3) Qualified teachers should be recruited and allowed to teach in private secondary schools.
- 4) Teachers without professional teaching qualifications, if recruited should be immediately sent for further training to acquire basic teaching qualification.
- 5) Government should investigate and monitor thoroughly, the available resources both material and human before approval is given for the commencement of new schools. This is because a conducive environment is necessary for effective teaching and learning.

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